

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF TEACHER'S ACTIVITY IN SPECIALIZED PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract: This article discusses the specific features of the teacher's activity in specialized pre-school educational organizations.

Key words: Educational system, specialized pre-school educational institution, educator, Vital. There are specific aspects of the educator's activity in specialized pre-school educational organizations. Adapting children with physical and mental disabilities to social life and directing them to professions are the main goals of educators. The activity of special educational institutions is managed by the state. Such events provide an opportunity to implement the state's policy on special education, to ensure the uniformity of the curriculum and programs.

A person changes throughout his life. This change can be in different forms, content, appearance. Deep, extensive changes occur during childhood. During this period, the physical and spiritual qualities of a person develop effectively. The mental and physical development of a person is a legal process and is formed in various processes of the individual's activity. Development of children and adolescents includes both physical and mental processes. Since man is a biological being, the laws of nature also apply to him.

But these laws affect humans differently than other living beings. While other living creatures adapt to the external environment and use ready-made things for their survival, man, while living in society, produces useful things himself.

A growing person learns the world deeply and fully. On the other hand, the company affects the environment with its activities. A certain person develops by expressing his attitude to other people, things, and events. There are developmental factors in all activities of the student. The essence of all activities serves to enrich the world views of my child. On this basis, my child's cognitive processes will grow and develop, and this will be possible. Any activity, if it is properly organized from the point of view of pedagogy, has a positive effect on the development of intellectual and voluntary qualities of a person. A person plans his activities, sets a goal for himself, ponders over the final result, chooses materials. In these processes, a person does not just try, but looks for the best possible method, takes a creative approach.

In the state specialized preschool organization, the following groups are formed in accordance with the contingent of children from 2 to 7 years old with disabilities in physical or mental development:

- *for pupils with severe speech defects;*
- *for children with severe hearing impairments;*
- *for pupils with severe visual impairments;*
- *for children who are delayed in mental development;*

- *for children with mental retardation;*
- *for pupils with musculoskeletal disorders.*

Specialized kindergartens are fully provided by the state. In these organizations, correctional work with children with physical or mental developmental disabilities is organized in cooperation with doctors, pedagogues, defectologists, nurses and educators. Children are fed 4 meals per 12-hour work schedule and 5 meals per 24-hour group.

Children with disabilities in hearing, vision, locomotor apparatus, mental retardation, mental retardation are admitted to the specialized preschool educational organization.

Education should be educational in nature. This is the first requirement of didactics. This principle unites the whole system of the didactic principle and directs the realization of the main task of the auxiliary school - a certain way of comprehensive education of mentally retarded children. In other words, this principle determines the ideological direction of the entire education in schools. To what extent and in what ways can this principle be implemented in the conditions of an auxiliary school? The experience of the auxiliary school has convincingly shown the possibility of raising the right attitude to work in the students of this school, character competence in the academic and literary community, and thus creating the necessary ideas of their duty to Vital). Yonnmehi school is closely connected with the social life of our republic in various ways, and on this basis, it has the opportunity to organize socially useful events for students with mental retardation. Pupils of auxiliary school 47 take part with great interest in, for example, helping the community farm: harvesting, feeding young livestock, and other activities. The children's organization at the school successfully organizes duty at school and in the classroom, organizes various gatherings and other similar events. The ideological direction of the content of the educational material is of great importance in the comprehensive education of children. The auxiliary school program and textbooks necessarily assume that one or another educational material is understandable. However, the teacher should pay attention to the extent to which the students understand the material, without going through the formal passage of this or that material. In this regard, Abu Nasr Farabi thought about human intelligence and expressed the following opinion: "Let him have a love for knowledge and study, and be able to learn the knowledge he wants to learn easily without feeling tired" (Abu Nasr Farabi, " City of virtuous people". Tashkent, 1993). It is these thoughts of Farabi that are important in the education of auxiliary school students. Labor education is an important factor in the moral education of secondary school students. Right attitude towards work and public property is brought up in children's educational workshops during the training process. Special observations show that most of the students of auxiliary schools after finishing school get a job in production enterprises, they are honest about work and careful about public property.

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